

The Time-Independent Schrodinger Equation without using Energy as a Starting Point

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell N.B. Jan. 5, 2018

The time-independent Schrodinger equation is written terms of energy, namely using $V(x)$ the potential and E , the energy eigenvalue. In fact, the equation can be written as $\text{KE average}(x) + V(x) = E$ and so can be expressed in terms of a classical energy conservation equation at each point. KE average, however, in such a case is complicated and seems to contain various kinds of kinetic energy motion which only yields on average the classical kinetic energy. The purpose of this note, is to try to determine the form of the time-independent Schrodinger equation without any concept of energy. Only at the end of the discussion, will comparisons be made with classical conservation of energy. In such a discussion, it is assumed that particles undergo a zitterbewegung type motion which can be modeled by $\exp(ikx)$ $\hbar k$ being the momentum and that there are forces (related to a $V(x)$) in the one dimensional problem. The objective is to try to understand microscopically what is happening without immediate resort to a conservation equation.

Time Averages

Let us assume that a particle undergoes a kind of zitterbewegung motion which is complicated. It only moves with speed v on average. For motion in one dimension, zitterbewegung already exists in two dimensions (1), so matters are already complicated. Consider placing such a particle in a one dimensional box with a potential $V(x)$ which gives rise to $F(x)$ i.e. force depending on position. We wish to think in terms of force, as we do not want energy entering into the discussion at early stages.

It seems that a main assumption of this entire analysis is that one is taking time averages and that the time needed to establish the average may be very long. For example, it may be as long as the time to traverse the box. Thus, one is not considering any position or speed at a given x at any given instant time as in classical mechanics. This seems to be an underlying idea of quantum mechanics for bound states.

Consider any point x_1 which will have a force $F(x_1)$. Given that the particles are modeled by $\exp(-ikx)$ (forward moving particle), they have a certain probability to exist in a region the size of a wavelength $1/k$ and can interact with the force anywhere in this region. Thus, matters are already very different from classical physics. One may argue that for x_1 , one can $\exp(-ikx)$ and $\exp(ikx)$, i.e. the particle moving forward or backwards. (This should hold for any k .)

At this point an important question arises, namely what is the weight factor for $\exp(ikx)$ and $\exp(-ikx)$? Should it be ± 1 or can the two be out of phase in an arbitrary manner? Again, one must note that long time averages are being taken. If the phase is 1 or -1, the combination of

$\exp(ikx)$ and $\exp(-ikx)$ will be real, i.e. on average one will not see the extra dimension brought in by zitterbewegung, otherwise it will not. Furthermore, if phase is not 1 or -1, the combination will be imaginary implying a net flow of flux in one direction or the other. Now, one might insist, that for the average of all k (momenta) there should be not net flux at x_1 averaged over a long time. This would mean that some k would have positive flux values and others negative flux values at x_1 , but there is no reason for a particular k_1 to have positive flux and another a negative flux. Thus, it seems that one has to conclude that the phase is 1 or -1. We will choose -1 for convenience.

A second important issue that exists is the notion of considering different points x for a given k . In the previous paragraph we tried to argue that $\sin(kx_1)$ describes the phase between forward and backward moving particles with momentum $\hbar k$ at x_1 . One may ask why one would not use $\sin(kx_2 + d_2)$ for point x_2 with d_2 being some constant? Certainly there could be a forward and backward moving particle at x_2 (over the averaging time, not necessarily at the same time instant) and one expects the phase to be such that there is no flux. Point x_1 has a force $F(x_1)$ and x_2 , a force $F(x_2)$. For small averaging times, this might perhaps be the case, but for longer averaging times this would mean that $F(x_2)$ is determining the value of d_2 . The problem with this seems to be that the particles are not points, but exist over a wavelength range. Thus, a particle with momentum k at x_2 may have been imparted with momentum at a point x some distance from x_2 . Thus, it is not clear why there should be any d_2 value on average. An alternative argument is that one may have a potential (or forces) that are symmetric about the origin. In such a case, changing x to $-x$ should yield the same result, which it will for $\sin(kx)$ at every point (i.e. specific parity). (This would apply to $\cos(kx)$ to have positive parity. Here we use $\sin(kx)$ for convenience.)

This leads to a very important result, namely that one describe a momentum $p = \hbar k$ by $\sin(kx)$ for the entire length range even though it has a force field. This is amazing as it is the exact description one would use if there were no forces. The long time average effect of the force is due to scattering the particle into various $\sin(kx)$ values, each looking like a particle that is bouncing between two walls with no potential. Thus, one should be able to model the system by the expression:

$$\sum p \sin(px) \quad \text{where } p \text{ is a weight factor for the particular } p \quad ((1))$$

The next step is to consider the effect of the force $F(x)$. Given that it is argued that one shifts from one $\exp(ik_1x)$ value to $\exp(ik_2x)$, mathematically a factor of $\exp(i(k_2 - k_1)x)$ will cause this change. Thus, one might expect that one could model the effect of the force $F(x)$ by:

$$\sum_k g_k \exp(ikx) \quad \text{where } g_k \text{ is a weight factor based on } F(x) \text{ i.e. how the force is distributed.} \quad ((2))$$

Next, one may argue that the system comes into resonance, with many scattering reactions occurring. There will be some time length for the various scatterings to produce the average

results of the resonance. One may call this the period, as the system may be repeating itself over and over. Thus, one may argue that there is a kind of cycling occurring.

Consider a specific momentum value k . In such a case, over a long period of time, one may expect a state with k_1 and weight $f(k_1)$ scatter with the force portion gk_2 to create a state of k . This can occur in many ways so one has the term:

Sum over p and j such that $p+j=k$ $f_p \exp(ipx) g_j \exp(ijx)$ where p and j (multiplied by \hbar) are momentum values.

These various scatterings will occur during the cycling time and combined with $a_k \exp(ikx)$ representing the particle in the k state without any scattering with a_k being some function of k may yield the following equation:

$$a_k \exp(ikx) + \text{Sum over } p \text{ and } j \text{ such that } p+j=k f_p \exp(ipx) g_j \exp(ijx) = \text{Factor } f_k \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

For a resonance one does not want the weights to change so the Factor can be set to the cycling frequency. f_k is the original probability for having state k and shows that one is in resonance, i.e. cycling brings one back to the probability with which one started. At this point, no concept of energy has entered the discussion.

Link to Energy Conservation

At this point, one has a number of unknowns in ((3)) namely a_k , g_k from the force, f_p the weights of the scattered states and the cycle time. Thus, ((3)) is quite ambiguous. To attempt to determine these unknowns, consider some ideas from classical physics. In classical physics, a particle with momentum p has a kinetic energy $p^2/2m$. It was assumed that in quantum mechanics, one is dealing with complicated zitterbewegung particles, but that these have an average velocity of v and presumably a kinetic energy of $p^2/2m$. Thus, for ((1)), one can write an expression for kinetic energy as:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = [\text{Sum over } p p^2/2m f_p \sin(p/\hbar x)] / [\text{Sum over } p f_p \sin(p/\hbar x)] \quad ((4))$$

One can see that an x dependent normalization constant is needed to make sure that one is calculating an average.

If this average is to have meaning, it seems that there should be an associated conservation of energy equation, namely:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E \text{ where } E \text{ is the total energy.} \quad ((5))$$

The question now becomes whether one can relate ((3)) to ((5)).

First, consider writing ((5)) as:

$$\left[\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} f_p \sin(p/\hbar x) \right] + V(x) \left[\sum_p f_p \sin(p/\hbar x) \right] = E \sum_p f_p \sin(p/\hbar x)$$

Next, consider summing ((3)) over all k:

$$\sum_k a_k \sin(kx) + \left[\sum_p f_p \sin(p/\hbar x) \right] \left[\sum_j g_j \sin(jx) \right] = (1/\text{cycle time}) \left[\sum_p f_p \sin(p/\hbar x) \right] \quad ((6))$$

Equation ((6)) would match ((5)) if $a_k = f_p p^2/2m$.

In such a case, (1/cycle time) would equal E up to an \hbar . Thus, it seems that the classical energy conservation equation applied to the long time average of a scattering quantum particle in a force field can lead to the independent Schrodinger equation. (Note: the $\sin(kx)$ functions are linearly independent.) This is interesting, because the ideas of conservation of energy here only apply to a long term time average. There is much microscopic behaviour occurring in addition to the creation of a static looking spatial density and an average conservation of energy it seems.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems that one can consider modeling a quantum particle with zitterbewegung as $\exp(-ikx)$ and $\exp(ikx)$ for forward and backward motion. One can place such a particle in a one dimensional box with a force varying with x . First, it seems that over a long time average $\exp(-ikx)$ and $\exp(ikx)$ will combine to form a real function such as $\sin(kx)$. Secondly, this function $\sin(kx)$ will hold at all points x (and not become $\sin(kx + d^2)$ with d^2 being a constant dependent on x). This leads to the idea that one has different $\sin(kx)$ functions (solutions of a box with no potential i.e. $\sum_k f_k \sin(kx)$ with f_k as a weight). The scattering of the force can then be modeled by $\sum_j g_j \exp(ikj)$. In the system, there will be all sorts of scattering reactions, but for equilibrium one expects that over a cycle time, a k state and its scatterings will go back into a k state leading to the equation:

$$A_k \exp(ikx) + \sum_{j, q \text{ such that } j+q=k} \exp(ikj) g_k \exp(iqx) = b_k (1/\text{cycle time}) \exp(ikx)$$

Here g_k is related to the probability of the force delivering $\hbar q$ of momentum.

Alternatively, one can write a conservation of energy equation ((5)) using the idea of an average kinetic energy at each point x . The quantum particle is associated with a region the size of the wavelength, so the average kinetic energy is a rather strange entity, yet one can use it to create a classical mechanical looking equation. Comparing this energy conservation equation with the equation obtained considering only forces can lead to the time-independent Schrodinger equation it seems.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Is Quantum Mechanics contained in Special Relativity? (preprint, zenodo, 2018)